

THE ROLE OF HISTORICAL CITIES OF UZBEKISTAN IN FORMING THE SPATIAL-PLANNING STRUCTURE

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Annotation. *This article examines the role of historical cities of Uzbekistan in shaping the spatial-planning structure. During the long historical development of the cities of Bukhara, Samarkand, Khiva, Shahrisabz, Tashkent and Kokand, cities were usually formed in areas with favorable landscape conditions, that is, rich in natural resources and developed transport and communication opportunities. These factors are manifested as the main determinants of the spatial structure, functional zoning and architectural appearance of cities.*

Keywords: *Historical city, spatial-planning ground, photography, connection, natural geographical, area, center, functional zoning, determinant*

Introduction. The historical experience of urban development shows that cities are usually formed in areas with favorable landscape conditions, that is, rich in natural resources and with developed transport and communication opportunities. These factors are manifested as the main determinants of the spatial structure, functional zoning and architectural appearance of cities.

These patterns are clearly observed in the case of the historical cities of Uzbekistan - Samarkand, Bukhara and Khiva. These cities have long been located along water sources, fertile oases and major trade routes, in particular the Great Silk Road, which directly influenced their economic, social and cultural development. At the same time, historical centers were formed as urban systems with a unique compositional structure, morphological integrity and functional stability.

Natural and geographical factors - river systems, relief features and climatic conditions - play an important role in shaping the spatial-planning structure of cities. In particular, the location of the cities of Samarkand, located in the Zarafshan Valley, Bukhara, which developed in the ancient oasis system, and Khiva, which formed near the Amu Darya delta, directly determined their planning model. These natural conditions formed the basis for the compact or linear development of cities, the formation of transport routes and public centers.

as an important theoretical basis for the integration of modern architectural objects into these areas. Because new constructions must be formed in accordance with the scale, spatial rhythm, silhouette and compositional integrity of the existing historical environment. Otherwise, the visual and cultural integrity of the historical environment may be violated.

In this regard, in the process of integrating modern architecture and cultural heritage sites, it is necessary to deeply analyze the historical development stages of the territory, natural-landscape features, and functional-planning system. Such a comprehensive approach will ensure the harmonious and sustainable development of modern architecture while preserving the authenticity of the historical environment.

As a result, the placement of modern architectural objects in historical city centers should be carried out not only based on aesthetic or functional requirements, but also on the principles of preservation, adaptation and sustainable development of cultural heritage. This will ensure the harmonious integration of historical and modern layers and strengthen the spatial-compositional integrity of cities.

Main part: The historical experience of urban development shows that cities are mainly formed in areas with favorable natural and landscape conditions, that is, rich in water resources, climatically suitable and with transport and communication opportunities. These factors are the main determinants of the spatial-planning structure, functional zoning and architectural-compositional appearance of cities.

are clearly demonstrated in the case of the historical cities of Uzbekistan - Samarkand, Bukhara and Khiva. These cities were formed under the influence of natural and geographical conditions, water supply systems and trade and communication routes such as the Great Silk Road, and their urban structure is inextricably linked to these factors.

The climatic features of historical regions also had a significant impact on the architectural and planning solutions of cities. In conditions of a sharply continental climate, daily and annual temperature fluctuations, high solar radiation, wind directions, and the presence of water resources were considered the main factors in the formation of architecture. The building density, street networks, courtyard systems, and volumetric and compositional solutions of historical cities developed in accordance with the natural environment.

Natural landscape elements - relief, water arteries, green areas and climatic factors - formed the spatial-planning framework of cities. In particular, the territorial structure of the cities of Samarkand, located in the Zarafshan Valley, Bukhara, formed in the oasis system, and Khiva, which developed near the Amu Darya delta, is closely related to natural conditions. These factors determined the compact or linear development model of cities and ensured a harmonious synthesis of the architectural environment and the natural landscape.

Historical experience shows that the inextricable link between landscape and architectural environment is one of the main factors in the sustainable development of cities. The planning system of cities was formed on the basis of the principles of rational use of the territory and often acquired a semi-regular structure. This served to ensure the consistency and continuity of the spatial framework formed in the process of historical development in subsequent stages.

is especially manifested through panoramic perception. The city silhouette, the location of dominant structures and points of visual perception were formed inextricably linked with the relief and water systems. Water arteries - rivers and canals - marked the compositional axes of historical centers and played an important role in the formation of the city panorama. At the same time, mosques, minarets, madrasahs and other architectural ensembles served as the main dominant elements of the city silhouette.

In the urban structure, historical cores, central squares, and large ensembles serve as compositional centers, around which residential areas are formed. This indicates the existence of a hierarchical system in the spatial structure of cities and its harmonious development with the natural environment.

In this regard, in the process of integrating modern architectural objects into the historical environment, it is necessary to conduct a thorough analysis of the natural landscape features, climatic conditions, and historically formed spatial-planning structure of the territory. New constructions should be designed without violating the scale, silhouette, rhythm, and compositional integrity of the existing environment, but rather as an element that enriches it.

Historical of cities in the formation landscape factor complex to the character has be, he functional and aesthetic aspects each other harmony through manifestation From a functional point of view, cities are usually located near water sources, transport and communication routes, and trade routes, while aesthetically, their spatial and compositional appearance is formed through the harmony of the natural environment and architectural forms.

These patterns are also clearly observed in the historical cities of Uzbekistan. In particular, cities such as Samarkand, Bukhara and Khiva developed on the basis of natural and geographical conditions and water systems, and rivers and canals played an important infrastructural and transport role in urban life. Especially in the oases of Bukhara and Khorezm, water systems served as one of the main factors of the economic and territorial development of cities. Therefore, the panoramic image of historical centers was often formed in connection with water courses, and they were perceived as the "facade" of the city.

Historical sources, particularly in the case of cities depicted in 18th-century engravings (including Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara, and Khiva), clearly demonstrate that the terrain, water systems, and natural landscape of the area played an important role in shaping the appearance of the city. These images clearly demonstrate the inextricable connection between the city and its natural environment, spatial-compositional integrity, and the influence of the landscape on the architectural environment.

The unique and distinctive appearance of historical cities was formed mainly on the basis of the interaction of two main factors - the natural landscape and the planning-functional structure. Cities had compact or linear development forms in connection with relief features, water sources and green areas.

For example, in the historical centers of Samarkand and Bukhara, architectural ensembles, religious structures, and public centers were often located on relatively high points of the relief or in spatially distinct areas. This increased their importance as visual dominants and ensured the compositional integrity of the city panorama.

and compositional structure of historical cities is formed through the harmony between three main structural elements - natural landscape, architectural dominants and simple (mass) residential structures. This "triple system" plays an important role in the spatial perception of the urban environment and serves as a theoretical basis for the integration of modern architectural objects into the historical environment.

Historical urban planning practices effectively utilized the potential of the relief, with architectural dominants (towers, domes, ensembles) often placed on natural elevations. At the same time, natural barriers - small rivers, ravines, and elevations of the relief - formed spatial intervals within the urban area, enhancing compositional expressiveness.

In some cases, several dominant objects are combined to form an ensemble, providing a holistic and expressive view of the city panorama. This approach also has an important methodological significance in integrating modern architectural objects into the historical environment, as new devices must be placed in accordance with the existing dominant system.

Analysis of the urban panorama shows that in the central areas, architectural dominants are densely located, defining the main axes of the spatial composition. In the peripheral areas, dominant elements decrease, which reflects the hierarchical structure of cities and the laws of visual perception.

The vertical parameters of dominant architectural objects are often aligned with the high points of the natural relief, which further enhances the interrelationship between landscape and architecture. As a result, the harmony of natural and artificial elements in the urban panorama provides a high level of compositional integrity.

In this regard, in the process of integrating modern architectural objects into the historical environment, ensuring visual perception, harmony with the landscape, and compositional balance are important scientific criteria. New constructions should be designed as elements that complement and develop the historical panorama, without violating its integrity.

The landscape factor in the location of historical cities has a dual significance - functional and aesthetic. Functionally, cities were formed in areas close to water sources, trade routes, and transport and communication systems, while aesthetically, their unique appearance was created through the harmony of the natural environment and architectural forms.

three main components - natural landscape, architectural dominants and simple residential structures - is of great importance in the formation of urban composition. This triad system ensured the spatial integrity of the historical urban environment and determined its aesthetic and functional stability.

Historical experience shows that the planning structure of cities often developed in a semi-regular manner, adapting to landscape features. This allowed preserving the morphological appearance of cities and ensuring consistency in subsequent stages of development. As a result, the historically formed spatial framework also serves as an important structural basis in the process of modern development.

landscape and architectural environment is also clearly observed in the historical cities of Uzbekistan. For example, historical complexes such as the Registan ensemble in Samarkand, the Poi-Kalon complex in Bukhara, and the Ichan fortress in Khiva have formed the main dominants of the urban composition and are located in harmony with the relief and urban structure.

From this perspective, in the process of integrating modern architectural objects into the historical environment, it is necessary to deeply analyze the natural landscape features of the territory, the historically formed spatial structure, and the system of existing architectural

dominants. New devices should be formed as complementary elements, without violating the scale, silhouette, rhythm, and compositional integrity of the historical environment.

In conclusion, the spatial-planning structure of the historical cities of Uzbekistan is a complex and coherent system formed under the influence of the natural environment, in particular, landscape, relief and water systems. Taking into account this system, the harmonious integration of modern architecture and cultural heritage objects is an important theoretical and practical basis for ensuring the sustainable development of cities.

and table formed within the framework of this study shows that the process of integrating modern architectural objects in historical city centers should be carried out on the basis of landscape, spatial-planning structure and rhythmic-compositional systems. Especially in the case of historical cities such as Samarkand, Bukhara and Khiva, the harmony of the cultural landscape, historical ensembles and urban environment is manifested as the main criterion.

modern construction and reconstruction of historical areas is of great scientific and practical importance. Urban planning approaches formed on the basis of historical experience are expressed through the following main modules:

First, **the landscape-natural module is the main factor determining the location** and direction of urban development. Natural relief, water systems, climatic conditions, and natural boundaries formed the initial spatial basis of cities.

Secondly, **the architectural-spatial module is formed on the basis of the mutual harmony** of the building system and the landscape, ensuring the compositional integrity and spatial balance of historical cities. This module creates aesthetic harmony and order in the urban environment.

Third, **the rhythmic module** - formed by architectural dominants (tower, dome, public buildings), enhances the visual expressiveness of the city panorama and defines spatial hierarchy.

The landscape factor directly influences the planning system of historical cities and forms the basis for their typological formation. In this regard, historical cities can be divided into the following main types:

1. Cities developed linearly on complex terrain, along large rivers;
2. Cities formed on both banks of the river, in a complex relief;
3. Cities developed linearly on a relatively flat area;
4. Cities developed in a compact form on flat or complex terrain.

Conclusion: This typological approach is also typical for the historical cities of Uzbekistan. For example, in Samarkand, the relief and water system of the Zarafshan Valley had a strong influence on urban planning, while in Bukhara, a compact and dense urban structure was formed in the conditions of a flat oasis. The historical part of the city of Khiva (Ichan Qala) appears as a closed, clearly delimited and compositionally integral space.

Based on the analyses conducted, the following scientific conclusions were drawn:

First, the historical landscape is a crucial factor in the formation and development of cities. Landscape elements integrate with the urban structure to create a cultural landscape.

Secondly, natural and spatial conditions determine the planning structure of cities and ensure its stability. The landscape-natural module combines with the architectural-spatial module to form the unique compositional image of each historic city center. Scientific study of these modules serves to form a systematic approach in modern reconstruction processes.

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